

The Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectrum and the Structure of Rauwolfinine

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The structure of rauwolfinine has been established through NMR spectrum.

Rauwolfinine (Chatterjee and Bose, *Science & Culture*, 1951, 17, 13²⁰) was isolated from the Cochin variety of *Rauwolfia serpentina* Benth, homogeneity of the compound being established from an examination of its paper chromatogram as also from its X-ray powder data. The singular nature of the base was also confirmed by Professor C. Djerassi of Stanford University, U. S. A. whom the authors thank most cordially. From degradation studies (Bose, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 47, 311, 691; 1958, 35, 72), the essential details of the structure of rauwolfinine appear to be clearly established as in (I), the carbon skeleton being in full consonance with the biogenesis of the *Rauwolfia* alkaloids (Chatterjee, Pakrashi, and Werner, *Fortschr. der. Chem. Org. Naturstoffe*, 1956, 13, 346-443; Woodward, *Angew. Chem.*, 1956, 68, 13; Wenkert, *Experientia*, 1959, 15, 165; Leete, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 6338).

The elementary analyses of the base and those of its salts and other derivatives are in better agreement with the composition $C_{19}H_{24}N_2O_2$ rather than with $C_{20}H_{26}N_2O_2$. On this basis it was suggested by one of the authors (S. B.) that the ethyl group at C_{20} (vide structure II) which arises from its progenitor (III) by fission of the hydrated prephenate moiety (ring E, III) by retroaldol process (Wenkert, *Experientia, loc. cit.*) suffers degradation to the lower homologue (I) through oxidation followed by decarboxylation during the biosynthesis of the alkaloid. Such oxidation to a carboxyl has been observed in cylindrocarpine and cylindrocarpidine (Djerassi, Archer, George, Gilbert, Shoolery, and Johnson, *Experientia*, 1960, 16, 532) isolated from Brazilian *Aspidosperma* species belonging to the family *Apocynaceae*. Such biogenetic transformation (from II to I) suggested above, however, needs verification for final decision on the inclusion or exclusion of the formulation (II) for rauwolfinine. Since nuclear magnetic resonance spectrum seemed appropriate for deciding between (I) and (II), a pure sample of rauwolfinine was studied in

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deuteriochloroform solution employing a 60 megacycle instrument for examining the chemical shifts (Fig. 1).

(III)

The positions of the peaks are shown in cps referenced relative to the signals from tetramethylsilane (used as the standard).

The most important information about the structure of rauwolfine came from the NMR proton count by electronic integration, which demonstrated quite clearly the presence of 26 protons and thus obviously established the empirical formula of the alkaloid as $C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2$, instead of the equally acceptable $C_{19}H_{24}N_2O_2$ (from analysis), favouring the structure (II) for rauwolfine. Conclusive evidence of the formulation (II) for the base was adduced from the studies of the following chemical shifts.

(i) A triplet in the region 44 cps and the peaks around 85 cps (for splitting up of $-CH_2$ protons) emphasises the occurrence of ethyl side chain in rauwolfine.

Amongst other valuable informations were:

(ii) AB system of the type

(IV)

where R and R' are different substituents, the characteristic multiplet for four aromatic protons appearing around 437 cps.

(iii) The quartets centered round 397 cps are due to intramolecular hydrogen bonding between proton at C_4 and oxygen atom attached to β -carbon atom (II).

(iv) A tall signal at 164 cps typical of $-N.CH_3$.

(v) Several peaks around 260 cps (due to splitting of the hydrogen atoms of $-O-CH(OH)$ by the neighbouring protons) indicating the presence of a six-membered oxide

CH-C

ring and at 230 cps for $-CHOH$. The beautiful splitting of the 260 cps peaks may be assigned to the proton on C_{16} which couples its spin to the proton on C_{17} .

(vi) The signal at 182 cps for spin coupling of protons at C_{21} and C_{20} .

FIG. 1

The empirical formula, the nuclear magnetic resonance data, and the chemical informations provided earlier for rauwolfanine (*vide supra*), are thus combined in expression (II) which presents the most rational formulation for the alkaloid.

It was of further interest to observe in connection with elucidation of the structure of this base that acid hydrolysis of rauwolfanine gave an aldehyde, D.N.P.H. (melts with gradual decomposition above 210° and frothing continues till 255°) which was virtually identical with that prepared from deoxyajmaline, $C_{20}H_{26}N_2O$, by the action of 5 *N*- H_2SO_4 (Chatterjee and Bose, *Science & Culture*, 1955, 20, 606) or periodic acid (Woodward, *Angew. Chem.*, 1956, 68, 13).

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